

Thermal and mechanical properties of several phthalonitrile resin system

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Abstract: An aromatic ether phthalonitrile monomer and several kinds of self-catalyst monomers with NH₂- group and imide structure in the main chain were synthesized. Based on selected monomers, novel phthalonitrile resin systems with low melting temperature suitable for RTM process were prepared. After cured to 375 °C all the resins have excellent thermal and thermal-oxidative property with 5% weight loss above 510 °C and T_g (defined as peak temperature of tanδ) over 500 °C. Glass fiber reinforced composites based on one resin system (SPCN1010) had high retention rate at elevated temperature.

Key words: phthalonitrile resin, high-temperature resistance, self-catalyzed

1. Introduction

Phthalonitrile resins with many striking properties (i.e., outstanding thermal-oxidative stability, excellent mechanical properties, low water absorption and superior flame resistance) have potential uses in composite matrices, adhesives, films and electrical conductors PAT^[1-8]. A variety of phthalonitrile monomers containing aromatic ether^[9-11], imide^[12], hexafluoropropylidene^[13], sulfone^[14-15], bisphenol A^[16] and aromatic ether phosphine oxide^[1] linkages between the terminal phthalonitrile units have been synthesized. High temperature of melting transition is a common shortcoming for phthalonitrile monomers (usually >200°C)^[9-16]. Development phthalonitrile monomer with low melting temperature would be interesting both in the view of science and industrial applications.

Recently an aromatic ether phthalonitrile monomer and several kinds of self-catalyst monomers with NH₂- group were synthesized in our group as shown in Scheme 1^[17-18]. In this paper the thermal and mechanical properties of these cured monomers were discussed using thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) and Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA).

Scheme 1. Phthalonitrile monomers and phthalonitrile resin systems

2. Properties of aromatic-ether phthalonitrile/diamine system

The melting point of monomer 1A was around 190 °C tested by Differential scanning calorimetry

(DSC). After mixing with catalyst B in molar ratio of 5%, the cure reaction was investigated by rheological analysis. The viscosity of the blends remained below 1 Pa·s for a period of time (gelation time) at temperature of 195 °C and 210 °C. Then, a rapid increase in sample viscosity was observed until a glassy material formed. The gelation time at 195 °C was about 30 minutes, which was longer than the one about 15 minutes at 210 °C.

Figure 1 TGA and DMA curves of cured resin system based on monomer 1A and catalyst B

As shown in Figure 1, thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) at a heating rate of 10°C/min in nitrogen and air was used to test the cured resin with cure profile as 200 °C/2h+250 °C/5h+315 °C/5h+375 °C/5h. 5% weight loss temperature was 503 °C in air and 495 °C with 72% char yield at 900 °C in N₂. Furthermore the cured resin had very high T_g at 481 °C (defined by the tanδ peak temperatures) tested by DMA with single cantilever mode at a heating rate of 5 °C/min in N₂.

3. Properties of self-catalyzed phthalonitrile monomers

3.1 Thermal and mechanical properties of cured 2O, 2M and 2P

Figure 2 TGA and DMA curves of cured 2O, 2M and 2P

The monomers presented different melting point (T_m) tested by DSC, 121.7 °C for 2O, 172.5 °C for 2M and 130.9 °C for 2P, which reflected that T_m had much relationship with the amino group position. As shown in Figure 2, TGA curves showed all the three cured polymers had high temperature of 5% weight loss not only in N₂ (>520 °C) but also in air (>510 °C), which revealed high thermal and thermo-oxidative stability. In addition, the char yield of cured monomers at 900 °C was high over 70% in N₂.

In Figure 2 all the cured monomers possessed so much high T_g above 560 °C (defined by the

tan δ peak temperatures) tested by DMA. The onset temperature for storage modulus to decrease was about 490 °C for all the three composites because 500 °C was near the cured monomer's decomposing temperature.

3.2 Thermal and mechanical properties of cured 4O, 4M and 4P

Also the TGA showed that cured 4O, 4M and 4P retained 95% wt over 520 °C and exhibited char yields near 70.0% under N₂. On the other hand, cured 4O, 4M and 4P showed weight retention of 95% above 510 °C in air.

All those above analysis revealed that the introduction of autocatalytic group (amino group) imparted cured polymers excellent thermal stability instead of affecting the thermal property.

4. Properties of phthalonitrile resin with low curing temperature

4.1 Rheological and thermal properties of SPCN1010 under isothermal conditions

The cure of SPCN1010 was also investigated by rheological analysis. The viscosity of the blends remained below 1Pa·s for a period of time (gelation time) at desired temperature of 155 °C and 170 °C. The gelation time of SPCN1010 at 155 °C was about 90 minutes, which was longer than the one about 40 minutes at 170 °C.

When cured to 375°C for 5h, the temperatures of 5% weight loss for cured SPCN1010 were 528 °C in N₂ and 518 °C in air in figure 7, which revealed high thermal and thermo-oxidative stability. In addition, Char yield of cured SPCN1010 under N₂ was 74.4% at 900 °C. The storage modulus didn't commence to slowly decline until temperature increased up to 450°C and shown a T_g at 472°C. This is evidence that the polymers retained very good mechanical properties at elevated temperatures.

Figure 3 The TGA and DMA curves of cured SPCN1010

4.2 Mechanical properties of SPCN1010-glass fabric composite

The flexure properties and short beam shear strength of composite panels at room and elevated temperatures were summarized in Table 1. The flexure strength value was 728 MPa at room temperature and maintained 50% and 47% at the test temperature of 450 °C and 500 °C, respectively. The short beam shear strength of panels was 38.6 MPa at room temperature. Upon to 450 °C and 500 °C, the samples still had strength retention of about 67% and 44%, respectively. These demonstrated that the SPCN1010/glass composite retained very good mechanical properties at elevated temperatures.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of SPCN1010/glass composite

SPCN1010	Cure profile: 170/2+200/2+250/5+315/5+375/5(°C/h)		
	flexural strength (MPa)	flexural modulus (GPa)	short beam shear strength (MPa)
Room temperature	728	25.8	38.6
450°C	369(50.7%)	23.3	25.9(67.1%)
500°C	320(43.9%)	21.1	17(44.0%)

5. Properties of modified phthalonitriol resin system for RTM

In order to make the phthalonitrile resin suitable for RTM process, nitrobenzene was used to modify SPCN1010. As a result, both RBCN10 and RBCN20 maintain viscosity between 300 to 600 mPa·s at 140 °C for over 3 hours, which was tested by rotation rheometry. In addition, the thermal and mechanical properties were comparable with SPCN1010. 5% weight loss temperature of RBCN10 and RBCN20 were over 520 °C in N₂ with char yield over 70% at 900 °C and DMA didn't show a peak of tanδ until 500 °C.

Figure 4 TGA and DMA curves of cured RBCN10 and RBCN20

6. Conclusion

Not only the binary phthalonitrile/catalyst system but also the self-catalyzed phthalonitrile monomers can be cured to thermosetting polymer owning excellent thermal and mechanical properties, which means possible usage as high-temperature-using polymer materials. Modified phthalonitrile resin system with good processability for RTM also had good properties after cure. Furthermore the high char yield of cured resins at elevated temperature indicates that these monomers can be used as high temperature ablation material probably.

References

- [1] M. Laskoski, D. D. Dominguez, T. M. Keller, *Polymer* **2007**, *48*, 6234.
- [2] S. B. Sastri, T. M. Keller, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry* **1998**, *36*, 1885.
- [3] S. B. Sastri, J. P. Armistead, T. M. Keller, U. Sorathia, *Polymer Composites* **1997**, *18*, 48.
- [4] S. B. Sastri, J. P. Armistead, T. M. Keller, *Polymer Composites* **1996**, *17*, 816.
- [5] T. M. Keller, C. M. Roland, Us Dept of the Navy (Usna) Us Sec of Navy (Usna), USA, **1993**, p. 23.

- [6] T. M. Keller, *Journal of Polymer science Part C: Polymer Letters* **1986**, 24, 211.
- [7] M. Shoji, H. Nishide, *Polymers for Advanced Technologies* **2010**, 21, 646.
- [8] M. J. Sumner, M. Sankarapandian, J. E. McGrath, J. S. Riffle, U. Sorathia, *Polymer* **2002**, 43, 5069.
- [9] T. M. Keller, *Chemistry of Materials* **1994**, 6, 302.
- [10] T. M. Keller, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry* **1988**, 26, 3199.
- [11] T. M. Keller, D. D. Dominguez, *Polymer* **2005**, 46, 4614.
- [12] T. M. Keller, *Polymer* **1993**, 34, 952.
- [13] S. B. Sastri, T. M. Keller, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry* **1999**, 37, 2105.
- [14] T. M. Keller, T. R. Price, *polymer communications* **1984**, 25, 42.
- [15] T. M. Keller, T. R. Price, *polymer communications* **1985**, 26, 48.
- [16] M. Laskoski, D. D. Dominguez, T. M. Keller, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry* **2005**, 43, 4136.
- [17] B. Amir, H. Zhou, F. Liu, H. Aurangzeb, *Journal of Polymer Science Part a-Polymer Chemistry* **2010**, **48**, 5916.
- [18] H. Zhou, B. Amir, Z. H. Luo, F. Liu, T. Zhao, *Polymers for Advanced Technologies* **2011**, accepted with Number PAT-11-055-R2